

Some Differences Between Quantum and Classical Waves

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We take as our starting point the free particle classical action which may be written as $A = -Et + px$ if t and x are treated as independent variables. It is possible to find two relationships linking v (velocity) to x and t from $dA=0$. The first is the classical wave result $vp = E$ while the second is $p = Ev$ where $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ ($c=1$). Furthermore one may write $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ ((1a)) and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$. ((1b)) This may be generalized to two eigenvalue differential equations, but this immediately begs the question: Why do this? We argue that Lorentz invariant form $-Et + px$ represents scaling of both t and x . For example, p scales x and we argue there should be physical relevance to this. This physical relevance results in the wavelength proportional to $1/p$. In other words, $-Et + px$ represents more than velocity.

The treatment of the scaling for a quantum wave and classical wave differ, we argue, in that the former keeps E, t and p, x separate while a classical wave does not. In other words $pv = E$ applies to a classical wave which is described by $\cos(-Et + px)$. In other words, one takes ((1a)) and ((1b)) which separate E, t and p, x into two independent equations and takes account of scaling by combining the two (to include both x and t) i.e. creating the classical wave equation: $1/v \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dx} \text{ partial} W(x, t) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{ partial} W(x, t)$.

We argue that quantum mechanics on the other hand keeps ((1a)) and ((1b)) separate. The velocity (relativistic) $p = Ev$ is not a wave velocity. A solution to ((1a)) is $\exp(ipx)$ and to ((1b)) $\exp(-iEt)$. These are usually combined for a free particle to give $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ and a wave is described with a phase velocity $v_{\text{phase}} = E/p$. We prefer to keep $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ separate. For example, for two slit interference one does not make use of phase velocity or $\exp(-iEt)$. For a bound state one uses $p = Ev$, but a single free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ in $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(-iE_n t)$ appears after one has found E_n , using the $\exp(ipx)$'s in the sense that one does not include an $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ for each $\exp(ipx)$.

We argue that by separating E, t and p, x , the latter leads to a scheme for which there is "no time". It is true that the particle moves at a speed x/t , but $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ etc so p does not uniquely define velocity, rather it defines an impulse $2p = \int F dt$. Thus the scaling px which leads to an x, p only wave $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to an interaction. If the particle is moving freely and not interacting, then one has classical determinism i.e. $v = \text{constant} = x/t$. As soon as an interaction occurs, one changes from variables x, t which are linked to x, P conditional (x/p) and there is uncertainty in the position of x within a wavelength. The phase in $\exp(ipx)$ is only dependent on x not on the time the particle reaches x .

$\exp(ipx)$ thus represents a probability and one must consider a sum of different possible outcomes (as in a two slit experiment) in order to describe an interaction. This is very different from the local interaction of classical mechanics. Nevertheless for a bound state one makes use of the two formalisms i.e. $KE(x) = \sum_p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) = KE_{\text{classical}}(x)$.

We try to discuss some of these ideas in this note.

Classical Action -Et+px

The expression $A = -Et + px$, which is Lorentz invariant already appears in classical waves and in the solution for a photon from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations. In such a case the velocity for the wave is $pc = E$ or more generally $pv = E$ which follows from $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$. There is, however, a second velocity which one may obtain from $dA = 0$ by assuming $p = Ev$ namely: $dA = 0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$. This leads to $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ ($c = 1$) i.e. the relativistic velocity for a particle with rest mass. $A = -Et + px$ also appears in the Action theory for a particle with rest mass. In (1) we showed that taking either the relativistic $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1 - v^2}$ or nonrelativistic $A = \frac{1}{2} m_0 t v^2$, writing $v = x/t$ and varying x and t independently yields:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ ((1a)) and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \text{ ((1b))}$$

This leads to the solution $A = -Et + px$. One may find a relationship between x and t by using $dA = 0 = -t dE/dv + x dp/dv$ with $p = Ev$ as noted above.

Scaling

We wish to stress the importance of scaling in $A = -Et + px$ which appears both in classical waves, the photon EM wave and free particle Action -Lagrangian theory. We note that p scales x so there should be a physical length proportional to $1/p$ associated with x for motion. For a classical wave or EM wave this is the wavelength, but $pv = E$ in such cases. For a particle with rest mass $v = p/E$ which differs from wave velocity. Nevertheless px appears and we argue that there should be physical consequences. Thus mathematical scaling is an indication of the presence of a wavelength, we argue. The question becomes: How does one implement this?

Wave Behaviour

A classical or EM wave makes use of both space and time because its velocity is a wave velocity i.e. $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$. Thus ((1a)) and ((1b)) do not remain separated, but are combined so that x and t are together. Thus one creates the classical wave equations from ((1a)) and ((1b)) i.e.:

$$1/v^2 d/dt d/dt \text{ partial} W(x,t) = d/dx d/dx \text{ partial} W(x,t) \text{ with } pv = E \text{ ((2))}$$

For a quantum wave there is already a velocity which is not wave velocity $pv = E$. Thus it seems there is no reason to think of an $x-t$ wave $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Instead we suggest that ((1a)) and ((1b)) remain separate i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. We recap that the reason for using waves in the first place seems to be scaling. One may note that by separating $\exp(-Et)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ one has $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$ etc i.e. one cannot distinguish velocity from p alone. As a result one may have particles with different rest masses moving at very different speeds, but having the same p . One, however, expects the motion in free space to be that of a free classical particle. What is the point of $\exp(ipx)$ then? We argue that p is linked to impulse hits which also do not distinguish

velocity even in classical mechanics i.e. $2p = \int F(t) dt = \text{Impulse}$. Fast and slow particles impart the same impact if they have the same momentum change (from p to $-p$ for example).

Thus the scaling px implies a wave type structure $\exp(ipx)$ which has importance when interactions occur. In such a case one changes from the deterministic x, t variables with $v=x/t=\text{constant}$ describing free motion to x , and $P(x/p) = \exp(ipx)$ which describes an interaction in a probabilistic sort of manner. This differs from Newtonian mechanics. There is uncertainty during the reaction because the variable time is removed and one cannot follow the particle using x, t . One has to consider different possible schemes and apply an $\exp(ipx)$ to each and ADD because one has an OR situation of conditional probabilities. Thus the question: Which slit does the particle enter in a two slit experiment does not arise.

For a two slit apparatus, located at some position, one may send in a single electron. As the electron travels towards the two slits it moves with $v=x/t$ i.e. it seems completely classical. There is an $\exp(ipx)$ (no time) wave, however, associated with this motion with the phase associated to x , but not t . At the slits an impulse hit occurs, but one no longer uses x, t to describe the electron, but $\exp(ipx)$. There is uncertainty of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ not only in the direction of motion, but in all directions i.e. the slits should be about one wavelength apart. In such a case one has to consider a probability for the electron going through one slit or the other and ADD as in an OR situation. As an approximation, performed in many textbooks, one may draw two short parallel rays one from each slit each making an angle θ . Drawing a line perpendicular to the first ray at slit one to the second ray creates a right angle triangle which shows that ray two has traveled a distance from the second slit. Thus the two rays are out of phase and may interfere. In other words there may be no probability to have a ray coming out at an angle θ . Thus it is the momentum scaling which leads to the idea of uncertainty of position (i.e. wavelength proportional to $1/p$) and lack of time within an interaction and this leads to self-interference. After that the electron should move with a classical speed at the fixed angle towards the screen. No time is used to calculate the interference (or diffraction in the case of a single slit) even though the second ray travels a different distance and so should be associated with a different time if $t=0$ at each slit.

Momentum Versus Speed

As a recap, consider two particles with rest masses $m_1 \ll m_2$, but with $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$. In such a case, v_2 is small compared to v_1 . In a fixed amount of time particle v_1 will be much further ahead than v_2 , although both have the same $\exp(ipx)$ wave. At a given x regardless of time both have the same phase. It is the momentum wave which seems to be involved with interactions, but it is not associated with time i.e. one cannot follow the particle using x, t as it interacts.

As another comparison, if one has two identical electrons at x then if one has $\exp(ipx)$ and the other $\exp(ip(x+a))$ there is also interference.

Lack of Time During an Interaction

As argued above no time variable is used during a two-slit interference or single slit diffraction calculation. The same is true for a bound state problem. Instead of writing $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for a free particle, we keep $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ separate. For a particle interacting with $V(x)$ we

again use $\exp(ipx)$ alone i.e. no time is involved. In such a case, the potential creates impulses which change p to p_1 etc. so one has a distribution (without time) of:

$$W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

An overall energy is produced E_n which is then associated separately with $\exp(-iE_n t)$. In such a case it is not only the momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ which interacts with $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, but there is interference with other $\exp(ip_1 x)$'s. In particular if one wishes to take an average, say of kinetic energy at x , one has:

$$KE_{\text{average}}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/m \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((4))$$

(It is possible to have $V(x,t)$ in which case time does appear in the interaction, but we consider $V(x)$ here.)

Classical mechanical kinetic energy is $p^2/2m = .5mv^2$. This is associated with calculating work which causes acceleration which is a very different scenario from the $\exp(ipx)$ approach discussed above. For example:

$$dp/dt = F \text{ so } dp/dx \ dx/dt = F \text{ or } p/m \ dp = F \ dx \ \text{ or } p^2/2m = \text{work} \quad ((5))$$

One may, however, consider $p^2/2m$ as a property of a free moving particle. For example a particle with p_1 has kinetic energy of $p_1^2/2m$. If it undergoes an impulse and changes to p_2 , then it has kinetic energy of $p_2^2/2m$. Thus the average ((4)) which seems to combine a Newtonian acceleration picture with the momentum wave $\exp(ipx)$ does not seem to be a problem.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a free particle moves in free space as a classical object with a constant velocity. This is the full picture in classical mechanics. We argue, however, that the classical Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ suggests scaling of space due to momentum. For this to be physically implemented and assuming that t and x are independent for a quantum particle with rest mass, then somehow there are regions proportional to $1/p$ in space as the particle passes through, regardless of its velocity. In other words the particle has a phase $\exp(ipx)$ which only manifests itself if there is an interaction. For example, $p=m_1v_1 = m_2v_2$ with $m_2 \gg m_1$ implies $v_2 \ll v_1$. Thus speed is not the issue, but momentum mapped against distance traveled is important. We argue it is important because momentum is linked to impulses i.e. interactions. In such a case, one switches from the deterministic x,t variables to x, P conditional $(x/p) = \exp(ipx)$. In other words there is uncertainty or probability $\exp(ipx)$ within a $1/p$ region as the particle interacts. In other words two slits must be about $1/p$ in distance. In the probabilistic picture one considers different possible results from impulses and adds the corresponding $\exp(ipx)$ terms as an OR situation. This leads to interference results which are not seen in classical mechanics.

We argue this all happens because $A = -Et + px$ suggests p scaling for x . (There is also the case of E scaling time separately.) There are two approaches one may take. First, $dA = -E dt + p dx = 0$ is the classical wave or photon EM wave approach and leads to $pv = E$. In this case x and t are linked. One has $dA/dx = p$ ((1a)) and $dA/dt = -E$ ((1b)) and wishes to bring in p scaling i.e. create an eigenvalue equation, but x and t must be involved. Thus ((1a)) and ((1b)) must be combined to create the t - x linked classical wave equation $\frac{1}{v} \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial } W(x,t) = \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \text{partial } W(x,t)$.

For a quantum particle with rest mass one has a different velocity $p = Ev$. One does not need to link x and t in order to bring in momentum scaling of space. In other words we keep ((1a)) and ((1b)) separate. We do not write $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$, but $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. As a result, we consider $\exp(ipx)$ as a momentum wave linked to space (not time) associated with a free particle traveling through space and time i.e. $x/t = v$. Two particles with the same p , but very different masses, have different speeds, but at any given x (different times) $\exp(ipx)$ is the same and that, we argue, is what matters for impulse interactions. Thus the deterministic variables x, t are replaced with probabilistic ones $x, P(\text{conditional}) (x/p) = \exp(ipx)$. The particle has a distribution within a $1/p$ distance and one considers possible effects of interactions within this distance and adds the associated $\exp(ipx)$ values for each as OR probabilities. This leads to interference due to interaction. For example for a bound particle with $V(x)$ one has $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Action/Lagrangian Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)